

Reactions of Tungsten(VI) Oxytetrachloride with Organic Acids

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Preparation and properties of the compounds formed by the interaction of tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride with some organic acids have been studied and their structures discussed.

A general survey of the literature shows that some salts of tungsten have been prepared (this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 153) by the action of WCl_6 on some organic acids, but no work appears to have been done to prepare similar salts of $WOCl_4$ with organic acids. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of compounds of $WOCl_4$ with some organic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride was prepared by the method described earlier (this *issue*, p. 760). The organic solvents were dehydrated and distilled. The other chemicals used were of B. D. H. or E. Merck's 'extra pure' quality.

Low-melting acids in benzene were added in excess to $WOCl_4$ in CS_2 and refluxed on a water bath till the evolution of HCl had ceased. In the case of other acids these solvents were evaporated in an oil bath, the temperature of which was then raised 10-20° above the m.p. of the respective acid, and the heating continued till the evolution of HCl had ceased. The products obtained were repeatedly washed with benzene or other organic solvents till free of the acid and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Tungsten was estimated as WO_3 and the organic matter was found by difference. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated in a few cases by the combustion method.

All the compounds are coloured, very stable in dry atmosphere, and do not respond to the test for chlorine. These are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in ethanol. The compounds formed with lauric, myristic, palmitic, and stearic acids are, however, sparingly soluble in benzene and hydrolyse slowly on boiling with water; these are decomposed by acids and alkalis.

It is evident that one molecule of $WOCl_4$ reacts with four molecules of monocarboxylic and two molecules of dicarboxylic acids, the reaction being more vigorous with the latter and is completed in a comparatively short time. The hydroxy-acids react vigorously with $WOCl_4$ and the hydrogen of both the carboxyl and hydroxyl groups is displaced. Nitro-carboxylic acids give similar compounds to those obtained with carboxylic acids and hydroxy-acids. In all the cases the corresponding tungsten salts are formed.

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TABLE I

Acids.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Lauric	$\text{WO}[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{COO}]_4$	Ash	18.53	18.47	..	..	..	..
2. Myristic	$\text{WO}[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{12}\text{COO}]_4$	"	16.91	16.61	..	..	..	..
3. Palmitic	$\text{WO}[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{14}\text{COO}]_4$	Greyish brown	14.94	15.98	..	..	..	..
4. Stearic	$\text{WO}[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{16}\text{COO}]_4$	Brown	14.09	13.80	..	..	..	..
5. Benzoic	$\text{WO}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COO}]_4$	"	26.80	26.89	48.36	49.13	2.81	2.29
6. Crotonic	$\text{WO}[\text{CH}_3\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{COO}]_4$	Deep brown	34.30	34.06	..	..	..	..
7. Cinnamic	$\text{WO}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}]_4$	Brown	22.93	23.34	..	..	..	..
8. <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic	$\text{WO}[\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO}]_4$	Light brown	20.84	21.28	..	..	..	..
9. <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	Do	Brown	21.16	21.28	..	..	..	..
10. Malonic	$\text{WO}[\text{CH}_2(\text{COO})_2]_2$	Brownish black	45.64	45.53	..	..	..	..
11. Adipic	$\text{WO}[(\text{CH}_2)_4(\text{COO})_2]_2$	Black	37.09	37.79	..	..	..	..
12. Phthalic	$\text{WO}[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{COO})_2]_2$	Brownish black	35.63	34.84	..	..	..	..
13. Succinic	$\text{WO} \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \end{array} \right]_2$	Brown	41.87	42.58	20.97	22.23	1.798	1.852
14. Camphoric	$\text{WO}[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4(\text{COO})_2]_2$	Greyish brown	26.19	26.42	..	..	..	..
15. Salicylic	$\text{WO} \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{COO} \quad \text{COO} \end{array} \right]_2$	Brown	38.33	38.97	35.07	35.60	1.624	1.695
16. 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic	$\text{WO} \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{NO}_2)_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{COO} \quad \text{COO} \end{array} \right]_2$	Light brown	28.18	28.21	..	..	..	..